

Generating Licensure Examination Performance Models Using JRip Classifier: A Data Mining Application in Civil Engineering

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RESEARCH ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Received: May 26, 2023 Reviewed: June 19, 2023 Accepted: May 07, 2024 Published: June 28, 2024</p> <p> Copyright © 2025 by the Author(s). This open-access article is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.</p>	<p>The purpose of this study was to create performance models for civil engineer licensure examinations using the JRip classifier. It identified the attributes that were significant to the response attribute, generated prediction models using JRip classifiers of WEKA, and determined how likely a CE graduate pass the CE Licensure Examination. The respondents were obtained from the CE graduates of Cavite State University Indang Main Campus who took a CE board examination from November 2016 to May 2019. The results obtained indicated the significance of the subject AENG 65, as well as CENG 65B and CENG 130 in predicting the CE Licensure Examination. The CE graduates were predicted to fail if their grade of AENG 65 is greater than or equal to 3 and CENG 135 is less than or equal to 2.5, and if CENG 120A and MATH 21B are greater than or equal to 2.75 and CENG 106 is less than 1.75. It also further concluded that if DCEE27 is greater than equal to 2.5 and the CENG 22A is greater than equal to 3 and the grade of CENG 110A is less than or equal to 2.75, then the CE graduates would fail the Licensure exam.</p>

Keywords: *JRip, WEKA, Attribute, Licensure Examination, Civil engineering*

Introduction

A professional's license is a government-issued standard mark in the general public to present excellence, norms of conduct, recruitment criteria, and member protection measures, ensuring a high level of commitment, responsibility, skills, and quality in one's career (Dayaday 2018). Engineering has transformed the world, yet it is a conservative and slow-moving profession (UNESCO 2010). Engineers play such an important part in today's world, most countries are focusing on the concept of licensing this profession (Ferrer et al., 2015). Engineers Licensure Examination is a tool for evaluating and ensuring the quality of engineers who will work in a variety of manufacturing enterprises in the Philippines and abroad (Dizon, 2013). Licensure examination performance is among the output indicators of said normative funding system in the allocation of expenditures to state universities and colleges (SUCs), It influences part of the budget received by the institution. This is the reason why Higher Education Institutions are paying close attention to their graduates' licensure examination results (Lascano & Bansiong 2017; Tarun et al., 2014). The Cavite State University (CvSU), Indang, Cavite faced with the current situation, the school's programs, particularly those requiring board examinations, must continue to meet the growing demand for excellence since the national passing rate of Bachelor of Science in Civil Engineer (BSCE) in CvSU does not even reach 50% according to the Philippines Regulatory Commission (PRC) since 2016 to 2019. Currently, the school always strives for strong performance in board examinations in the domain of civil engineer licensure examination. Board examination reviews were done as a strategy by the department. There have been various attempts to find models for predicting licensure examination results; however, most research proposed a larger study with more independent factors and different approaches. For instance, Roehrig (1998) conducted a study to predict licensure examination performance among Physical Therapy graduates. To predict licensing exam scores, researchers used ACT scores, necessary and non-prerequisite grade point averages (GPAs), and interviews and recommendation scores (Roehrig 1988). Ong et al. (2012) used inferential approaches to determine the predictors of nursing graduates' licensure examination performance. College entrance examination intelligence test, nursing aptitude test, composite score of science, Math, and English exams, college grade point average, as well as pre-board examination performance were the variables employed.

On the other hand, Soriano (2009) focused his research on the cognitive as well as non-cognitive records of education graduates. In the confines of her study, her goal was to find the best indicators of LET success. She discovered that the respondents' LET performance was best predicted by their GPA in general education, college entry exam score, course, and gender. Thus, she recommended that a follow-up study involving other factors such as school schedule, reviews attended, Field Study evaluations, school environment, and instructor factor should be done. Other researchers used a descriptive–correlational strategy to discover the association between in-house review and LET performance (Fiscal & Roman, 2022; Amanonce & Maramag 2020; Roman, 2018). They discovered a substantial correlation between pre-board and LET outcomes. They suggested that a similar study be conducted for BEEd and BSEd content courses and fields of expertise.

The subsequent literature, on the other hand, justifies the capability of data mining methods in the prediction of student performance, which was regarded as useful in the development of the study's framework. According to Slezak et al. (2014),

to predict student performance in a course utilizing social network data, his co-authors used regression and machine learning approaches utilizing the R-project software as well as WEKA, respectively. They claimed that students' final ratings are closely tied with those of their friends. They were able to show that a student's final grade is related to those of their friends using multiple linear regressions. Likewise, Sembiring et al. (2011) used the kernel methods for data mining to examine correlations between student behavior and success and also to develop a model of student's performance predictors. They concluded from their research that data mining was particularly beneficial in predicting student final performance. Hence, utilizing WEKA Explorer and data mining can reliably predict students' overall course performance (Mellalieu, 2011). He also developed a decision support system prototype, which was deployed as ReXS, an interconnected collection of spreadsheets.

Analyzing this large amount of data is a difficult task, thus having the right tools and approaches for sorting large amounts of data is critical. Data mining is one of the techniques for transforming unstructured data into useful information and knowledge (Hastie, et al., 2009). By uncovering, learning, and knowing underlying patterns, trends, and structures, data mining automatically finds and analyzes vast amounts of data (Mita et al., 1981) and provides answers to queries that cannot be answered using traditional query and reporting approaches (Ahmeda et al., 2015). This study was conducted to look into the elements that influence BSCE board exam results. In detail, the study aimed to determine (1) which predictors were significant to students' performance on the BS Civil Engineering Licensure Examination (2) what BSCE Licensure Examination prediction models could be derived from the predictors and (3) how likely would a CE graduate pass the CE Licensure Examination based on the predictors? In doing so, the study's findings would serve as a basis for the department, college, and university, helping them to place greater emphasis on, revise, and emphasize the factors that improve BSCE-CvSU graduates' performance on the board examination.

Methods

Conceptual Framework

Han and Kamber (2016) illustrated the Knowledge Discovery Process (KDP) in their textbook "Data Mining: Concepts n Techniques, Second Edition", which served as the study's framework. The KDP was altered to meet the study's aims. Figure 1 shows the modified form.

Figure 1. *Conceptual Framework*

Research Design

Experimental research design and quantitative approach were utilized since the study dealt with determining the factors affecting the performance in Civil Engineering Licensure Examination and which predictors were significant to students' performance. An experimental design improves a researcher's capacity to establish causal relationships and draw causal conclusions by using accurate and accurate empirical measurement and control (Bell, 2009). Statistical approaches enabled the researcher to better understand and analyze the factors that influenced a certain subject using experimental design procedures. Such methods combine theoretical understanding of experimental designs with practical knowledge of the factors to be investigated (Hanrahan et al., 2004).

Research Participants

The participants in this study were BSCE graduates at CvSU Indang in Cavite, Philippines, who took the BSCE Licensure Examination between November 2016 and May 2019. The study only looked at first-time takers. Enumeration in its entirety was used. The study included 156 participants.

Data Description

The PRC provided the ratings of all BSCE board examinees who passed and failed the exam, while the Registrar's Office or the Department of Computer and Electronic Engineering (DCEE) provided the list of grades and computed weighted average for all subjects.

Research Procedure

Permission was obtained from the relevant academic department prior to data collection. In order to meet ethical guidelines, the database administrators anonymized each student's academic records. After that, the co-author received the anonymized data. It was impossible to create any kind of bond with anyone because of this. Concerns about admission criteria and access to student admittance information were handled by senior academicians as well as top university authorities. There was an internal system for cross-checking the grades given to each student for every subject.

Data Analysis

Duplicate records were removed from the data that was contained in various tables. Similarly, records with empty values were removed. The researchers used JRip of WEKA, which is a classification algorithm, to generate models. In WEKA, applying the best classifier JRip to the dataset attribute evaluation was done first. The purpose of the attribute evaluation was to find attributes that were significant to the response variable, which was the BSEE licensure performance. Figure 1 shows the distribution of data for all attributes.

CENG 111	Timber Design	1-5
CENG 120A	Theory of Structures	1-5
CENG 125A	Construction Cost Engineering	1-5
CENG 130	Steel Design	1-5
CENG 140	Transportation Engineering	1-5
CENG 145	Water Resources Engineering	1-5
CENG 150	C E Laws, Contracts, Specifications and Ethics	1-5
CENG 155	Construction Methods and Project Management	1-5
CENG 190	Inspection Trips and Seminar	1-5
CENG 196	C E Competency Appraisal 1	1-5
CENG 197	C E Competency Appraisal 2	1-5
CENG 198	C E Competency Appraisal 3	1-5
CENG 199	On-The-Job Training	1-5
CENG 21A	Safety Management	1-5
CENG 22A	Statics of Rigid Bodies	1-5
CENG 23A	Dynamics of Rigid Bodies	1-5
CENG 24A	Engineering Economy	1-5
CENG 25A	Mechanics of Deformable Bodies	1-5
CENG 50	Elementary Surveying	1-5
CENG 55	Building Design	1-5
CENG 60	Higher Surveying	1-5
CENG 65B	Building system design	1-5
CENG 75A	Geotechnical Engineering 1 (Soil mech.)	1-5
CENG 80A	Hydraulics	1-5
CENG 85A	Route surveying	1-5
CENG 90A	Theory of structures	1-5
CENG 95A	Building design 2	1-5
CENG 101A	Bridge Engineering	1-5
CENG 106	Highway Design and traffic safety	1-5
CENG 111	Pre-stressed concrete design	1-5
CENG 116	Special topics in structural engineering	1-5
CENG 200	C E Project	1-5
CENG 26	Engineering Management	1-5
CENG 70	Construction materials and testing	1-5

CHEM 1-B	General chemistry	1-5
CPEN 2	Fundamentals of computer programming	1-5
DCEE 23B	Advanced engineering math for CE	1-5
DCEE 27	Basic Electrical Engineering	1-5
DCEE 28B	Basic Mechanical Engineering	1-5
DRAW 21	Engineering drawing 1	1-5
DRAW 22	Engineering drawing 2	1-5
DRAW 23	Computer aided drafting and design (cadd)	1-5
ECON 3	General economics with 1 r r	1-5
ENGL 1	Study and thinking skills in english	1-5
ENGL 2	Writing in the discipline	1-5
ENGL 6	Speech communication	1-5
ENGL 7	Scientific reporting / thesis writing	1-5
MATH 11A	Integral calculus	1-5
MATH 12A	Differential equations	1-5
MATH 21B	Analytic geometry	1-5
MATH 22A	College algebra	1-5
MATH_4	Advanced algebra	1-5
MATH_9	Numerical analysis	1-5
MATH 10A	Differential calculus	1-5
MATH 4B	Plane trigonometry	1-5
PHYS 1B	Mechanics and thermodynamics	1-5
PHYS 2B	General physics 2	1-5

Classification Method Used

STAT 1A	Engineering probability and statistics	1-5
BSCE LE Performance	This is the BSCE performance on licensure exam which makes use of 2 classes	Passed, Failed

The researchers used JRip of WEKA. It uses sequential covering algorithms to create ordered rule lists and uses a propositional rule learner dubbed "Repeated Incremental Pruning to Produce Error Reduction (RIPPER)." Growing a rule, pruning, optimization, and selection are all stages of the algorithm (Gupta et al., 2016; Veeralakshmi, 2015). The algorithm performs cross-validation of the eight (8) folds including a set of attributes and the related outcome, commonly referred to as the target

or prediction attribute, in order to predict the outcome of the datasets. The accuracy of JRip is 78.2051% which is the best classifier shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: JRip Percentage of Accuracy

Attribute Evaluation

ClassifierAttributeEval with the search method of Ranker was used to determine the rank of the subject who had the most impact in CE Licensure Examination. As seen in Figure 3, the AENG 65 followed by CENG 65B to CENG 130 were the top 20 subjects that had the most impact in CE Licensure Examination. However, all of the predictors were kept in the dataset because they may be required for a certain occurrence. Kovacic (2010) had a similar experience, where despite their insignificance found during feature selection, all available predictors in his dataset were used in the classification tree analysis.

== Attribute selection 8 fold cross-validation (stratified), seed: 1 ==

average merit	average rank	attribute
0.096 +- 0.013	1 +- 0	3 AENG 65
0.045 +- 0.01	3 +- 0.71	29 CENG 65B
0.027 +- 0.017	9.6 +-12.73	16 CENG 190
0.021 +- 0.018	9.8 +- 6.08	2 AENG 27
0.038 +- 0.027	9.9 +-17.84	26 CENG 50
0.016 +- 0.012	11.3 +- 9.48	41 CENG70
0.018 +- 0.022	14.6 +-14.78	13 CENG 145
0.014 +- 0.018	14.6 +-14.82	27 CENG 55
0 +- 0	15.9 +- 4.28	36 CENG106
0 +- 0	16.3 +- 3.38	35 CENG101
-0.004 +- 0.014	18.6 +-17.04	28 CENG 60
-0.002 +- 0.003	20.5 +- 8.69	39 CENG200
-0.007 +- 0.019	20.6 +-19.26	51 ENGL 1
-0.002 +- 0.003	21.3 +-10.65	37 CENG111
-0.011 +- 0.03	21.8 +-22.9	57 MATH 21B
0 +- 0	22.1 +- 8.64	42 CENG1-3
-0.003 +- 0.005	22.1 +- 9.73	38 CENG116
-0.001 +- 0.004	23.6 +- 5.59	8 CENG 120A
0 +- 0	23.9 +- 5.11	19 CENG 198
0 +- 0	24.5 +- 3.64	10 CENG 130
-0.002 +- 0.004	25.3 +-10.77	43 CENG21
-0.004 +- 0.008	27 +-12.28	7 CENG 115
-0.005 +- 0.009	27.1 +-13.15	22 CENG 22A
0 +- 0	27.1 +- 5.18	46 DCEE28B
-0.003 +- 0.009	27.9 +-12.77	33 CENG 90A
0 +- 0	28.1 +- 2.37	58 MATH 2A
-0.008 +- 0.009	29.3 +-14.8	64 PHYS 2B
0 +- 0	29.4 +- 4.06	49 DRAW 23
-0.003 +- 0.008	29.9 +-10.04	1 AENG 24A
-0.007 +- 0.012	30.4 +-14.39	40 CENG26
-0.007 +- 0.01	30.6 +-15.7	65 STAT 1A
-0.008 +- 0.01	30.9 +-16.54	23 CENG 23A
-0.005 +- 0.006	31.5 +- 5.72	9 CENG 125A
-0.004 +- 0.003	32.5 +- 2.87	50 ECON 3
-0.008 +- 0.012	34 +-12.64	60 MATH 9
-0.012 +- 0.011	35 +-17.48	25 CENG 25A
-0.007 +- 0.017	36.4 +-14.2	54 ENGL 7
-0.013 +- 0.025	36.9 +-22.62	44 DCEE 23B
-0.011 +- 0.008	38.8 +-11.05	47 DRAW 21
-0.012 +- 0.012	39.9 +-12.61	59 MATH 5
-0.017 +- 0.022	40 +-20.17	21 CENG 21A
-0.012 +- 0.006	40.3 +- 5.95	11 CENG 135
-0.015 +- 0.01	40.5 +-13.54	30 CENG 75A
-0.014 +- 0.018	41.9 +-16.68	55 MATH 11A
-0.015 +- 0.005	42.8 +- 6.02	61 MATH10A
-0.016 +- 0.016	42.9 +-17.95	31 CENG 80A
-0.017 +- 0.014	43.3 +-15.63	24 CENG 24A
-0.022 +- 0.021	43.9 +-21.05	15 CENG 155
-0.022 +- 0.019	44.5 +-18.63	3 CENG 105A
-0.017 +- 0.012	45.1 +-13.28	56 MATH 12A
-0.018 +- 0.006	46.4 +- 4.77	18 CENG 197
-0.027 +- 0.022	48 +-21.97	6 CENG 110A
-0.022 +- 0.012	48.4 +-11.79	53 ENGL 6
-0.019 +- 0.01	48.9 +- 5.16	63 PHYS 1B
-0.023 +- 0.011	50.1 +- 5.96	45 DCEE27
-0.024 +- 0.011	50.3 +- 8.58	4 CENG 100A
-0.022 +- 0.007	50.3 +- 6.67	52 ENGL 2
-0.022 +- 0.012	50.3 +- 9.47	32 CENG 85A
-0.023 +- 0.007	51 +- 7.62	12 CENG 140
-0.025 +- 0.013	51 +-10.56	14 CENG 150
-0.025 +- 0.012	51.4 +- 5.56	48 DRAW 22
-0.026 +- 0.011	52.3 +- 5.4	17 CENG 196
-0.028 +- 0.011	54.4 +- 8.11	20 CENG 199
-0.027 +- 0.007	54.9 +- 6.01	34 CENG 95A
-0.036 +- 0.009	60 +- 5.1	62 MATH8

Figure 3. Attribute Evaluation

JRip Prediction Model

JRip is a RIPPER-based inference as well as a rule-based learner that aims to provide propositional rules for classifying components (Hindle et al., 2009). Figure 4 shows the prediction model created by JRip utilizing WEKA in an 8-fold cross-validation. The following are the four rules:

If AENG 65 is greater than or equal to 3 and CENG 135 is less than or equal to 2.5, the CE graduates would likely fail the CE Licensure Examination.

If CENG 120A and MATH 21B are greater than or equal to 2.75 and CENG 106 is less than 1.75, the CE graduates would likely fail the CE Licensure Examination.

If DCEE27 is greater than or equal to 2.5 and CENG 22A is greater than or equal to 3 and CENG 110A is less than or equal to 2.75, the CE graduates would likely fail the CE

Licensure Examination. Otherwise, the CE graduates are predicted to pass the CE Licensure Examination.

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JRIP rules:
=====

(AENG 65 >= 3) and (CENG 135 <= 2.5) => CLASS=FAILED (25.0/4.0)
(CENG 120A >= 2.75) and (MATH 21B >= 2.75) and (CENG106 <= 1.75) => CLASS=FAILED (11.0/1.0)
(DCEE27 >= 2.5) and (CENG 22A >= 3) and (CENG 110A <= 2.75) => CLASS=FAILED (6.0/0.0)
=> CLASS=PASSED (114.0/9.0)

Number of Rules : 4

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Figure 4. JRip Rules

JRip Confusion Matrix

The overall percentage of correct classification of JRip is 78.21% as shown in Figure 5. There are only 34 incorrectly classified instances, which indicates that the model is incorrect for only 29.79% of the cases in the dataset.

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===== Confusion Matrix =====

  a  b  <-- classified as
95 15 |  a = PASSED
19 27 |  b = FAILED

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Figure 5. Confusion Matrix

Conclusion and Future Works

In light of the results, the researchers concluded that the subject AENG 65, as well as CENG 65B through CENG 130 in the Figure 3 attribute evaluation, were significant to the response attribute, which was CE performance in the licensure examination. This was based on the results obtained in attribute selection. As for the prediction model obtained using the JRip classifier, it can be concluded that if the grade in AENG 65 is greater than or equal to 3 and the grade in CENG 135 is less than or equal to 2.5, the CE graduates would likely fail the CE Licensure Examination. In addition, if their grades in CENG 120A and MATH 21B are greater than or equal to 2.75 and their grade in CENG 106 is less than 1.75, the CE graduates would likely fail the CE Licensure Examination. It can also be concluded that if their grade in DCEE27 is greater than or equal to 2.5, while their grade in CENG 22A is greater than or equal to 3, and their grade in CENG 110A is less than or equal to 2.75, the CE graduates would

likely fail the CE Licensure Examination. Other than these specified rules, the CE graduates are predicted to pass the Licensure examination. These models can be of help to civil engineers as they identify students who need special review assistance in specific subjects and eventually increase the licensure exam passing rate.

References

- [1] Ahmeda, R. A. E. D., Shehaba, M. E., Morsya, S., & Mekawiea, N. (2015). Performance study of classification algorithms for consumer online shopping attitudes and behavior using data mining. *2015 5th International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies* (pp. 1344–1349). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSNT.2015.50>
- [2] Amanonce, J. C. T., & Maramag, A. M. (2020). Licensure examination performance and academic achievement of teacher education graduates. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 9(3), 510–516. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v9i3.20614>
- [3] Bell, S. (2009). Experimental design. In *International Encyclopedia of Human Geography* (pp. 672–675). Elsevier.
- [4] Dayaday, M. G. (2018). *Factors affecting the performance in the board examination of electronics engineering: University of Southern Mindanao graduates* [Unpublished master's thesis]. University of Southern Mindanao.
- [5] Dizon, N. (2013). Academic achievement in the learning domains and performance in licensure examination for engineers among LPU's mechanical and electronics engineering graduates. *International Journal of Management, IT & Engineering*, 3(8), 347–378. <https://research.lpubatangas.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/IJMIE-Academic-Achievement-in-the-Learning.pdf>
- [6] Ferrer, F. P. (2015). *Performance in the engineer licensure examinations* [Master's thesis, Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Maynila, Philippines].
- [7] Fiscal, R. R., & Roman, A. G. (2022). Pre-licensure examination as predictor of licensure examination for teachers result. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 11(1), 136–142. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v11i1.22063>
- [8] Gupta, A., Mohammad, A., Syed, A., & Malka, N. (2016). A comparative study of classification algorithms using data mining: Crime and accidents in Denver City, USA. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 7(7), 374–381. <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2016.070749>
- [9] Han, J., & Kamber, M. (2016). *Data mining: Concepts and techniques* (2nd ed.). Morgan Kaufmann.

- [10] Hanrahan, G., Zhu, J., Gibani, S., & Patil, D. G. (2004). Chemometrics and statistics – Experimental design. In *Encyclopedia of Analytical Science* (2nd ed., pp. 8–13). Elsevier.
- [11] Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R., & Friedman, J. (2009). *The elements of statistical learning: Data mining, inference, and prediction* (2nd ed.). Springer.
- [12] Hindle, A., German, D. M., Holt, R. C., & Godfrey, M. W. (2009).
- [13] Automatic classification of large changes into maintenance categories. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Program Comprehension* (pp. 30–39). IEEE.
- [14] Kovacic, J. Z. (2010). Early prediction of student success: Mining student enrolment data. In *Proceedings of the 2010 InSITE Conference* (pp. 647–655). Informing Science Institute.
- [15] Lascano, E. A., & Bansiong, A. J. (2017). Five-year licensure examination performance of library and information science graduates. *Asian Journal of Contemporary Education*, 1(1), 1–9.
- [16] Mellalieu, P. J. (2011, July–August). Predicting success, excellence, and retention from students' early course performance: Progress results from a data-mining-based decision support system in a first year tertiary education programme. In *International Conference of the International Council for Higher Education* (Miami/Ft. Lauderdale, Florida) (pp. 1–9).
- [17] Mita, S., Yamazoe, Y., Kamataki, T., & Kato, R. (1981). *Cancer letters data mining: The textbook*.
- [18] Ong, M. B., Palompon, D. R., & Bañico, L. (2012). Predictors of nurses' licensure examination performance of graduates in Cebu Normal University, Philippines. *Asian Journal of Health*, 2(1).
- [19] Roehrig, S. M. (1988). Prediction of licensing examination scores in physical therapy graduates. *Physical Therapy*, 68(5), 694–698.
- [20] Roman, A. G. (2018). Fractal dimension analysis of pre-board and licensure examination results of teacher education graduates. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(2), 40–49.
- [21] Sembiring, S., Zarlis, M., Hartama, D., Ramlina, S., & Wani, E. (2011). Prediction of student academic performance by an application of data-mining techniques. *Management and Artificial Intelligence*, 6, 110–114.

- [22] Slezak, D., Schaefer, G., Vuong, S. T., & Kim, Y. S. (Eds.). (2014). *Active media technology: 10th International Conference, AMT 2014, Warsaw, Poland, August 11–14, 2014: Proceedings* (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 8610). Springer.
- [23] Soriano, H. (2009). Factors associated with the performance of USM College of Education graduates in the 2007 licensure examination for teachers. *USM R&D*, 17(2), 151–159.
- [24] Tarun, I. M., Gerardo, B. D., & Tanguilig, B. T. (2014). Generating licensure examination performance models using PART and JRip classifiers: A data mining application in education. *International Journal of Computer and Communication Engineering*, 3(3), 202–207.
- [25] UNESCO. (2010). *Engineering: Issues, challenges and opportunities for development*. UNESCO Publishing.
- [26] Veeralakshmi, V. (2015). Ripple-down rule learner (RIDOR) classifier for IRIS dataset. *International Journal of Computer Science Engineering*, 4(3), 79–85.

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